

DEVELOPING CRITICAL THINKING THROUGH EDUCATION TECHNOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the concepts of developing critical thinking through education technology. Since the special technology of critical thinking has been developed so it is based on three phases of learning gradually replacing each other: Call, Making sense, Reflection. Each of these phases is briefly described in this scientific article. Also, teaching critical thinking does not rely exclusively on education technologies, but it is undeniable that a wise application of technology in class can give it a considerable boost.

Keywords: critical thinking, education technology, research skills, mental skills, analytical approach, Call, Making sense, Reflection.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье анализируются концепции развития критического мышления с помощью образовательных технологий. Так как разработана специальная технология критического мышления, то она основана на трех фазах обучения, постепенно сменяющих друг друга: Призыв, Осмысление, Рефлексия. Каждый из этих этапов кратко описан в данной научной статье. Кроме того, обучение критическому мышлению не опирается исключительно на образовательные технологии, но нельзя отрицать, что разумное применение технологий в классе может дать ему значительный толчок к развитию.

Ключевые слова: критическое мышление, образовательные технологии, исследовательские навыки, умственные способности, аналитический подход, призыв, осмысление, рефлексия.

INTRODUCTION

The labor market imposes increased requirements on all employees of the organization, including new employees, among whom there are many university graduates. Young professionals should quickly adapt and be included in the new job. To do this, they need to be not only professional and competent, but also mobile and sociable, have a professional mindset and be able to work in a group. "The quality of

teaching and the necessary skills for the formation of moral values among youth in Uzbekistan can be called a complex issue and a common problem for the whole society. There is universal enrollment in high school, where the majority of students do not achieve expected results by academic standards in being able to “apply” their knowledge and use it for reasoning. Employers are dissatisfied with the skills of their employees, especially non-cognitive skills such as "taking responsibility for their actions", "self-motivation" and "creativity"¹. “Local educational institutions do not prepare young people for how to behave in a digital environment and cope with the stresses of professional life. In this regard, "agility" ("nimbleness") will become a decisive soft skill for promoting Digital Uzbekistan in the current labor market”². In this direction, emphasis was placed on the use of technologies for the development of critical thinking in the educational process, both among university teachers and students from various cities and regions.

METHODS

“Critical thinking refers to your ability to evaluate facts so that you can fully understand a topic or issue and develop an effective solution. Objectivity is vital in creative thinking because it allows you to analyze a problem without allowing assumptions, emotions or biases to influence your judgment”³. The technology for the development of critical thinking was developed at the end of the 20th century in the USA by Charles Temple, Ginny Steele and Curtis Meredith. It synthesizes the ideas and methods of technologies of collective and group ways of learning, as well as cooperation and developmental learning. “The purpose of this technology is to develop the mental skills of students, which are necessary not only in studies, but also in everyday life: the ability to make informed decisions, work with information, analyze various aspects of phenomena, etc. The technology is based on the creative cooperation of the student and the teacher, the development of an analytical approach to any material among students”⁴. The technology is not designed to memorize the material, but to formulate a problem and search for its solution, and is general pedagogical above the subject. This is a universal penetrating system of techniques, open to dialogue with other pedagogical approaches and technologies.

¹ Yugay, E. V. (2021). Digital culture and its influence on value aspects of human being. ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science, 12 (104), 422-425. SoI: <http://s-o-i.org/1.1/TAS-12-104-29> Doi: <https://dx.doi.org/10.15863/TAS.2021.12.104.29>

² See above

³ Yugay Evgeniya Viktorovna. (2022). INFORMATION AND DIGITAL LITERACY: THEIR CONCEPTS AND SKILLS. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6945140>

⁴ <https://www.ya-roditel.ru/professionals/pedagogika/tekhnologiya-razvitiya-kriticheskogo-myshleniya/>

DISCUSSION

Teaching critical thinking goes much deeper than adding some technological flavour to the classroom: developing critical thinking in the 21st century is a matter of blending technology with tried and true pedagogical methods. Making students think critically starts with asking the right questions, both to them and to yourself. Open-ended questions, for example, foster critical thinking more than multiple choice quizzes because they encourage them to think for themselves and come up with original solutions rather than choose among a pool of pre-determined answers: with open-ended questions, you are putting students in a situation where the concepts of right and wrong are debatable and they are expected to defend their arguments with solid proof, which is an essential part of critical thinking.

But before you ask questions to your students, you should first and foremost question yourself as a teacher: are you actively involving them in your lessons or expecting them to listen passively and regurgitate information? If your teaching style is closer to the latter, you are not encouraging critical thinking. Critical thinking does not mean your students should challenge your authority: it means they should be supported in forming their own opinion on debated issues and in understanding how and why things work rather than accepting it as fact. Approaching critical thinking from this angle makes it applicable to all subjects: while it is true that some topics are more suited to debate while others involve a lot of rote memorization of unquestionable facts, any class can be made into a training ground for critical thinking if you encourage students to understand why two times two makes four instead of limiting yourself to giving them multiplication tables to learn by heart.

So, a special technology of critical thinking has been developed, which is based on three phases of learning, gradually replacing each other:

1. **“Call.** The main purpose of this phase is to arouse the student's interest in the topic. By increasing attention to the subject or object, there is an increase in the indicators of cognitive activity, which is based on the desire for knowledge. At this stage, the role of the teacher can be called passive, but at the same time significant, since attention and observation of the behavior of students is required.
2. **Making sense.** This phase is characterized by the supply of new information. Its source can be a teacher and the student himself in the form of independent study of the material. Delivery style, quality and quantity play a significant role. Lack or excess of these factors may affect the desire to explore the topic. The comprehension stage allows you to apply a filter to the questions posed in the challenge phase. A significant part of them is eliminated, and the remaining questions become more substantive.

3. **Reflection.** The feedback stage, in which students analyze data, exchange opinions, give their point of view. It is at this stage that the connection of one's own experience with the new knowledge that has appeared in the process of three steps takes place”⁵.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, “the study of the impact of digital communications on culture and society is associated with the presence and need to solve a number of emerging problems, where our state pays special attention to determining the goals, objectives and measures for the implementation of the domestic and foreign policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the field of application of information and communication technologies”⁶. Thus, teaching critical thinking does not rely exclusively on education technologies, but it is undeniable that a wise application of technology in class can give it a considerable boost. The role of the teacher is to observe, which can be included, but still involves providing students with the opportunity to work independently and experience personal experience and introduce new knowledge into an individual development plan.

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⁵ <https://www.ya-roditel.ru/professionals/pedagogika/tekhnologiya-razvitiya-kriticheskogo-myshleniya/>

⁶ Евгения Югай Цифровая культура и общество: проблемы их взаимоотношений в условиях глобализации // ОИИ. 2021. №7/С. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/tsifrovaya-kultura-i-obschestvo-problemy-ih-vzaimootnosheniy-v-usloviyah-globalizatsii> (дата обращения: 24.09.2022).